

Intentional Islanding of Power Systems through Self-embedding Learning

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Abstract—Intentional islanding is a procedure aiming to divide the power grid into several segments to ensure the stability of the whole system in case of a failure. This paper proposes an unsupervised deep neural network to handle the problem of intentional islanding. We propose to use a self-learning neural network to improve the generalisation performance of the islanding task. In addition, we use a merging technology to assign isolated buses to their neighbour’s label. Experiments are carried out on several grid cases to illustrate the effect of our solution.

Index Terms—Self-learning, deep learning, k-means, intentional islanding, smart grid, power system

I. INTRODUCTION

The stability of the power system is an important issue; the design of modern smart grids should take emergency cases into consideration, and offer self-healing features through smart solutions that enhance the reliability when faults occur. Intentional islanding offers such a solution, aiming to divide the grid into several independent, stable partitions, each operating sustainably, in order to prevent cascading failures that might lead to a blackout. Methods towards islanding are mainly based on optimisation approaches to find the optimal combination of the cut.

Recently, the area of deep learning has shown huge potential in computer vision and natural language processing (NLP). Fully connected neural networks are the main structures to deal with these tasks; they are composed of the linear layer where each input node has a connection with the output nodes. In computer vision, convolutional neural networks [1], [2] have introduced great improvements compared to previous traditional machine learning approaches. The base unit of the convolutional neural network involves the convolution operation that utilises sliding windows on the input feature map. Due to the nature of the intentional islanding problem,

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 833955.

few machine learning approaches have attempted to provide a solution, such as unsupervised learning [3]. We aim to follow an enhanced unsupervised approach to handle the intentional islanding problem, while ensuring the grid stability. Our key contributions are the following:

- We combine unsupervised deep learning with traditional k-means to deal with the intentional islanding problem.
- We use a merging technology to help with the coarse clustering result, guaranteeing the stability of the power system.

II. RELATED WORK

Intentional islanding is translated into a graph partition problem with an NP-hard computational complexity. Several approaches have been proposed over the years, with current solutions focusing on splitting strategies that assure the existence of coherent generators in each island [4]. It is often modelled as a combinatorial optimisation problem, with objectives that include the minimisation of the load-generation imbalance or the minimisation of the power flow disruption. With respect to the latter, proposed solutions are based on a graph theory technique known as spectral clustering. This method is used to determine the partitions of the graph representing the power grid, by utilising the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the associated matrix [5].

The authors in [6] propose a spectral k-embedded clustering algorithm that provides the islanding solution by solving the generalised eigenvalue problem. The number of clusters is determined by the grouping the coherent generators and the weight as well as the normalised Laplacian matrices used are obtained through the graph representation of the power system. After normalising the eigenvectors, the authors select those related to the k-1 lowest eigenvalues and apply their algorithm to obtain the islanding solution. A constrained spectral clustering algorithm is introduced in [7], able to offer the islanding solution while achieving minimal power flow disruption and ensuring that the islands contain coherent generators. The

proposed technique solves the related eigenproblem only once, regardless of the number of created islands, improving the efficiency of the solution in cases of large-scale power systems. Using the minimal power flow disruption as the objective function, the authors in [8] introduce a novel two-step spectral clustering algorithm, that avoids islands with isolated loads by satisfying the required coherency of the grouped generators. At the first stage, the generators are grouped using the normalised spectral clustering technique, and at the second stage the islanding solution is achieved using constrained spectral clustering. The computational efficiency of the above methods is adequate, but the lack of dynamic constraints in the clustering procedure raises the possibility that the power system may be partitioned into unstable islands, that may eventually cause a total blackout. Moreover, when solving the intentional islanding problem with the objective of minimum power imbalance, these solutions cannot achieve polynomial time, as the corresponding algorithms require a computational time exponential in order [9].

In [10] the islanding problem is formulated through a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model. By using graph theory, the authors transform the splitting strategy into a graph partitioning problem and propose a solution based on the objective of minimum number of lines that require disconnection. The optimal islanding solution is obtained through a recursive procedure, after considering the subgraph connectivity constrains. The authors of [11] also formulate intentional islanding as an MILP problem and propose an algorithm that ensures minimal power flow disruption irrespective of the number of islanded partitions. Utilising a pre-processing technique, the complexity of the problem is reduced, and the algorithm computes the relevant trees that connect each generator to the minimum number of nodes in the graph.

Traditional approaches fail to provide time-efficient solutions when solving the intentional islanding problem with respect to minimising the power imbalance at the formed islands. This work aims to address this issue by introducing a deep learning architecture for the power system splitting strategy. The proposed self-learning neural network is trained in an unsupervised manner and is able to offer efficient islanding results, while ensuring minimum load-generation imbalance and also satisfying the requirement of coherent generator grouping.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section describes our method of using a self-learning neural network for the intentional islanding task. Note that our solution does not require labelled data, it is totally unsupervised. Our technique consists of 3 parts: a) graphical representation of the power system, b) self-learning neural network and c) clustering. The flowchart of the proposed solution is shown in Figure 1.

A. Graphical Representation of the Power System

Since power grids are intricate, dynamic integration of electric instances such as generators, buses and transformers

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed solution for intentional islanding.

render the representation of the whole system difficult. To better implement the interface with the deep learning solution, we first convert the whole grid into a graph where each bus is represented by a vertex and each transmission line and transformer is converted into an edge. For better simulation, we abandon other instances like loads and generators. Note that to ensure the stability of the whole power grid when we abandon some elements, we run powerflow of the system before the graphical transformation, then extract the electric parameters as the values of the graph converted from the grid. The powerflow shows the status of the power system when it reaches a relatively stable condition.

To implement the interface with the deep neural network having tensors as the input, while our graph representation of the power grid consists of the nodes and edges, we follow [12] to convert the nodes and edges into one tensor; the first step is to construct the similarity matrix S and the degree matrix:

Fig. 2. The structure of our self-learning neural network.

$$S = N \dots N^T, \quad (1)$$

$$D = \text{diag}(d_0, d_1 \dots d_n), \quad (2)$$

where N is the node feature from powerflow and d_i is the degree of the i -th node. Finally, the input feature for the self-learning neural network is expressed by:

$$X = D^{-1}S \quad (3)$$

B. Self-learning Neural Network

In [3], the solution towards intentional islanding mainly focuses on the direct features from power flow, which simply takes the powerflow as the input of K-means cluster machine learning metrics. We aim to overcome the issue where those features are hand-crafted and may be highly correlated and cannot not express the recent power of deep learning approaches. To address this problem, we build a self-learning neural network, aiming to improve the generalisation performance of the clustering result. Figure 2 indicates the structure of our proposed self-learning network.

Our self-learning network consists of two parts: the model structure and the loss function. Recently, embedding learning has been suggested in literature as a mechanism to improve the generalisation performance for deep learning, especially in the area of computer vision and NLP. Our model is mainly constructed using a linear layer inspired by [12], where several linear layers are utilised to reconstruct the input features. We follow a similar protocol to reconstruct the graph at the end of the structure. The model structure is divided into two phases: encoder and decoder. The first computes the embedding of the input features and the latter aims to recover the input features.

To recover the graph representing the power system, we add a reconstruction loss function to reduce the error between the predicted features and the label-input graph. The loss function is defined as follows:

$$L_{recover} = \underset{y_i}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^n \|y_i - x_i\|^2, \quad (4)$$

where y_i is the predicted feature from our self-learning neural network and x_i is the input feature. The L2 loss function is used to minimise the Euclidean distance between the two features. In addition, to further improve the generalisation performance, sparsity constraints have also been added:

$$L_{recover} = \underset{y_i}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^n \|y_i - x_i\|^2 + \beta KL(\rho || \hat{\rho}) \quad (5)$$

The $KL(\rho || \hat{\rho})$ is the Kullback-Leibler Divergence that evaluates the distance from ρ over $\hat{\rho}$. ρ is a hyper-parameter that is usually set to a small value like 0.01 and $\hat{\rho}$ is the average of the activation output of the hidden layer in our self-learning neural network. This loss can be solved by the backward propagation which has been widely applied in deep learning. This reconstruction loss does not need any label to tell which partition is the best, it is totally self-supervised.

When the loss function converges, we extract the hidden layer as the embedding expressed by the whole graph.

C. K-Means Graph Clustering

In subsection III-B we discussed how the self-learning neural network is constructed in a self-supervised manner for more generalised feature learning. In this subsection we analyse the use of the learned features for graph partition - intentional islanding. We utilise K-Means, a typical machine learning technique towards unsupervised classification, to handle the problem.

The input features are extracted from the embedding of the self-learning neural network, which is expected to have a good generalisation performance, representing the initial power system. Then, k-means manually set up n clusters, the whole k-means calculates the distance of every node to the clustering centre and then updates the centre. The process is stopped when k-means converges or hits the upper bound of the iteration number.

In some cases there is an error after the graph partition process, as demonstrated in Figure 3, where we execute the solution to give a coarse partition result with $n = 3$ partitions. The two buses with the yellow colour are isolated from the others. For this reason we use a merging technology to assign these independent buses to the nearest cluster. We first check the colour of every neighbouring bus and if one bus is not connected to the bus with the same colour, we start to merge it to its closest neighbour as defined by the euclidean distance. The closest bus could be selected by the physical distance as well.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we examine the performance of our proposed solution towards intentional islanding on several power grids. We use test cases from the pandapower [13] library for the

Fig. 3. The coarse clustering result.

evaluation. Subsection IV-A describes the model implementation and subsection IV-B discusses the evaluations results.

A. Model Implementation

As mentioned in section III, the first step towards our solution for intentional islanding is to convert the power grid into a graph format. We first run the powerflow provided by the pandapower library and we extract the results especially for buses and lines for the graph representation. Then we construct the graph using the buses as nodes and lines and transformers as edges.

Our neural network consists of five linear layers, where the number of parameters of each layer are n , 128, 64, 128 and n respectively, n being the number of nodes in the graph. We train the self-learning loss for 10000 iterations, using Adam as the optimiser, and the corresponding learning rate is 0.0001. Our deep learning platform is Pytorch [14] which integrates the most functions of deep learning such as data-loader and optimisation. We extract features from the third layer of the neural network with 64 parameters, then use k-means from the Sk-learn [15] library. After the prediction is finished, we assign the same colour for the buses which are predicted to be in the same cluster for visualisation purposes.

B. Evaluation Results

To evaluate the performance of our proposed solution for intentional islanding, we provide the results on the test cases of pandapower which correspond to real power systems. Figures 4 and 5 demonstrate the final results. From top to bottom are the original grids, the clustering results and the merging results respectively. From left to right are the power grids as taken from pandapower: case 9, 14, 30, ieee 30, 57 and 145.

As observed in the figures, simple cases are easy to handle, such as case 14 which is successfully partitioned into three parts without any isolated buses. Larger cases tend to be harder to predict ideally and in some cases there exists an independent bus. Our proposed merging technology can relieve this phenomenon, by assigning the independent buses to their nearest neighbour.

Table I presents the numerical results of power grid cases 9 and 30. It includes the load-generation imbalance before and after our merging technology and the number of lines to be

Fig. 4. Clustering results for cases 9, 14 and 30.

Fig. 5. Clustering results for cases ieee 30, 57 and 145.

cut to perform the islanding. The load-generation imbalance is given by the sum of absolute values in each island. Our technique is compared with a method based on the GAP framework proposed in [16].

TABLE I
NUMERICAL RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED SOLUTION.

Method	Imbalance	After merge	Lines
Case 9 [16]	128.95	128.95	2
Case 9 proposed	384.95	71.04	2
Case 30 [16]	286.95	286.95	7
Case 30 proposed	120.04	53.82	10

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a novel method that combines the area of unsupervised deep learning with the problem of intentional islanding in power systems. The graph partition problem is formulated for this islanding problem, then a deep learning encoder-decoder structure is constructed to learn generalised features for k-means to finish the clustering. In addition, a merging technology is used to assign the isolated independent buses to their nearest neighbour. The proposed solution performs well on the test cases, especially on those with small number of buses.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 833955.

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